

**GRADUAL EROSION OF STATUTORY SCHEDULES OF REGISTRARS AND
OTHER PROFESSIONAL ADMINISTRATORS AS IT AFFECT THE
ADMINISTRATION OF UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA: A REVIEW**

by

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Abstract

The erosion and usurpation of the statutory schedules of Registrars and Professional Administrators of Universities is fast becoming a disturbing trend. The essence of this paper is to identify factors responsible for the usurpation with a view to determining the way forward by awakening the consciousness of Registrars and Professional Administrators to their statutory roles and functions in the University system using literature review as research methodology. It was found out that low educational qualifications of some Registry staff often lead to their low performance. This often leads to usurping of their duties by academic staff that are assumed to perform better. The paper recommends that university's professional administrators should be vastly knowledgeable by studying up to Masters and even Doctorate degree level to improve initiatives, engagements, new technology knowledge for an efficiency and quality job performance. This will bring back their reputation in our universities and restore back their duties respectively.

Keywords: Registrar, Professional Administrators, Statutory Schedules.

Introduction

There is looming danger posed by the continuous erosion of the statutory schedules of Registrars and professional administrators in the Nigerian universities. This could be seen in instances where most of the major players in the Registry Department, like the Legal Officer, Information and Protocol Officer, and Academic Planning Officer, have been gradually transferred to the Office of the Vice-Chancellor and are directly answerable to him, while the Law describes the Registrar as the Chief Legal Officer, Chief Spokesperson, etc. of the University.

But the above scenario seems to be more worrisome in the fact that stakeholders in the system, including the administrators themselves, seem not to bother about this trend which could be due to a number of factors that range from a variety of interests bothering on ignorance,

conveniences, in-house fighting, corruptive tendencies, unhealthy ambition, politics, a lack of synergy, compromise by even the Registrars and Professional Administrators in some cases, and worse of them all, incompetence. Unfortunately, the Registrar is gradually becoming more of a figurehead, powerful only in the books but practically rendered irrelevant.

In reviewing this situation, this paper outlined the following points as its trend of argument:

1. Origin of the role of Professional (Career) Administrators in universities
2. The basic statutory roles of Registrars and Professional Administrators in the Nigerian University system
3. The usurpation of the statutory roles of Registrars and Professional Administrators and their effect on the Administration of Tertiary institutions
4. The way forward

Clarification of Key Concepts

For easy understanding of this work key concepts like registrar, professional administrators, statutory schedules are clarified as used in this work.

Registrar: means the officer heading an administrative department of an organization also referred to as the registry department. The term Registrar is mostly used in the registry department of tertiary institutions.

Professional Administrators: are officers in the Registry Department, who assist the Registrar in carrying out his statutory administrative duties as against other non-teaching staff, who are regarded as professionals or academics in administration by virtue of the administrative functions they also perform.

Statutory Schedules: are functions and duties to be carried out and performed by officers as provided in a legal document establishing an organization, for example, the law establishing universities provides for statutory offices and their functions.

Origin and Importance of the Role of Registrars and Other Professional (Career) Administrators of Universities.

The importance of the role of Professional Administrators in the University system cannot be underestimated, but it is most often misunderstood because little is known about how administrators came to become an integral part of the university system. This misconception informs the kind of relationship that exists between academics and administrators today because,

rather than concentrate on their peculiar job schedules and prove their worth, most administrators spend time competing with the academics, whom they always feel look down on them.

Adegbite (2007), described this development by stating that the universities started as a solitary community of teachers and students. It is an institution with an early and principled origin. Its initial forebears included the Academy of Plato and the Library of Alexandria and it shows a line of ancestry in the Western World that traces the path of civilization itself. Even though the ancient Greeks and Romans had a firm system of advanced education, the University as it is known today is a product of the middle ages. It was not until the 12th and 13th centuries that structures of organized advanced education in the form of faculties, libraries, prescribed courses of study, examinations, diplomas, etc., developed. Thereafter, the university as an institution, as well as the system of its administration, began to undergo a lot of transformation.

According to him, in the initial years, the management of the university was a typical of practicality. There were limited administrative duties to be done and no distinct group of administrators was required to carry these out. The leader of the community managed the businesses of the University with the support of students and few members of staff.

Eventually, the expanding and changing demands of higher education, affected the simplicity of administration. The improvement in student admission was a primary factor in the transformation that followed. Size of staff increased, and so also the scope of budgets and physical facilities, and controlling became problematic and difficult. Consequently, the necessity to have a separate group of people to execute the administrative and management roles of the academic community. The essence of university administration, therefore is basically intended to bring and maintain order into a system which otherwise could have been difficult to control and manage.

The decision to engage administrative personnel in the management of tertiary institutions is a constructive and purposeful one. The major reason is to exclude academics from mainstream administration and management of tertiary institutions with a view to enabling them focus on the main objectives of the university, which are: teaching, research, and community development.

Adegbite (2007), listed the likes of Olu Awojobi, legal-sound minds like Gani Fawehinmi, profoundly medically celebrated scholars like Oshun Tokun, and literary giants like Wole Soyinka and Chinua Achebe, amongst others, indicate that there was a time when Nigerian universities really thrived. The same University had first class Academic Administrators like

Kenneth Dike, Hezekiah Oluwasanmi, and Ade-Ajayi, as well as University Professional Administrators like Simon Adebo, Femi Eperokun, and Moji Ladipo.

Some questions can arise on why the discrimination of the two professions like, why is it that the same institution of scholars (an ivory tower) is also producing nowadays Academic Administrators and Professional Administrators without grounded knowledge of Management, respect for propriety in administration, and academic standards? Why has the University System transformed into a community of unlettered and unruly managers who compromise standards and work for their personal interests rather than the development of society?

Weber (1968), in his theory of bureaucracy made it clear that every organisation and society requires the existence of a specific number of specialists and bureaucrats (administrators) to undertake the functions of administration within a formal organisation and establishment. The ivory tower is no exception, even from the days of monastery universities, where clerks and later Registrars were appointed to oversee non-academic matters such as finances, public relations, secretarial work, and the welfare of students. Hence, the basic work of a professional administrator is to help the academic gain stability and expertise in his field and be able to function with little or no distractions or stress.

Based on the above origin as stressed by Adegbite (2007), all stakeholders in the University are guilty of this. Academics struggle to come into administration while the administrators, who are meant to support the academics and facilitate the main objectives of the university, are busy underestimating their importance.

The Statutory Role of the Registrars and Other Professional Career Administrators in the Nigeria University System.

There is necessity for Professional Administrators because, according to Babatola (2017), the activities of academics cannot be complete when they do not have corresponding competent, experienced, or dependable administrator to manage their work processes and organisation of functions beyond teaching in the classroom and conducting research in the laboratories, where there are divisions of labour and specific roles to be played by the various employees.

Having expatiated on the origin of administration in the university system, with emphasis on the role of Professional Administrators, it is pertinent to further provide, for the purpose of this topic,

the basic statutory roles of Registrars and other Professional Administrators as provided and derived from the laws establishing universities.

The Professional University Administrators carry out their responsibilities in accordance with the law, statutory powers and obligations, organizational policy and guidance, and other university rules and regulations. They are in the system to support, manage, and operate policies and procedures in order to ensure their effectiveness in achieving the vision and mission of the institution.

According to Babalola (2017), the role is what translates to what is describable or surmounted as a duty and obligation, an expectation or responsibility, a principal or practice, a measure of character and conduct, an attitude or behaviour, an assumed status, and the direction of activity or actions, among others, which make a player an agent, an employee, a citizen, a partner, a careerist, or a professional to be regarded as a catalyst in any organization, association, platform, or partnership. Hence, the role within the contextual framework is assured to be a predetermined engagement or commitment.

Babalola (2017), further explains that a role is a step to be taken and to be played by those who have been given certain opportunities or tasks to perform. Yet the assured role can only be played within the context of a definite acceptability, resource capacity, and productive engagement; it is a role that is recognized and supported by the power templates that create the duty and the personality of the office. It is not a role that can be performed without the existence of the institution, the organization, and the player as a partner, stakeholder, or employee engaged to function, react to, and influence specific matters in a relationship and the objectives of pursuits. Another equally important aspect of determining what constitutes a role for Babalola (2017), is the capacity to stimulate, motivate, and ensure that a role player is able to play his role and function as expected.

This was captured by Awosisi (2020), that in a typical university, particularly a public university in Nigeria, there is a "command" structure and an "ascension" line. For professional administrators, the command structure has the Registrar as the "General Commander" and therefore the ascension aspiration of the administrator is to become the University Registrar. Professional University Administrators are, by this arrangement, directly in line of succession to the Registrar, who is the head of the Registry.

The typical enabling statute of a Nigerian university defines the Registrar and assigns specific statutory functions to that office. For example, the Nasarawa State University statute states that "the Registrar is responsible to the Vice Chancellor for the day-to-day administration of the affairs (other than academic and financial affairs) of the University" – Nasarawa State University Act, 2000, First Schedule Section 6 Sub-section (1). It therefore follows that the duties and responsibilities of a Professional University Administrator is derived from those of the Registrar as may be delegated or assigned.

Based on this, as Awosisi (2020) cited Etehe (2001) who stated that the functions of the Registrar can be broken down as follows:

a) Day to Day

The Registrar is the Chief Administrative Officer who is responsible to the Vice-Chancellor for the day-to-day administration of the affairs (other than academic and financial affairs) of the University, 1st schedule 6(1).

b) Secretarial

He/she Provides Secretarial services to all committees of Council, Senate and Congregation, as well as other ad-hoc Committees that may be set up from time to time.

c) Statutory

The Registrar is Secretary to Council, Senate, Congregation and Convocation and all Sub-Committees. He/ She provide information and relevant documents needed at meetings to aid the taking of informed decisions and ensure that all decisions taken are recorded and implemented.

d) Advisory

As the Chief Adviser and custodian of the rules, regulations and records of the University, the Registrar must be equipped with relevant information so as to guide appropriately.

e) Symbolic

The Registrar as the symbol of authority and gateway to the real authority that resides in the Vice-Chancellor must be present at meetings, to ensure that proceedings are in accordance with laid down rules.

f) Facilitator

The Registrar is the facilitator in matters affecting the teaching staff and implementer of policy/decisions of the University.

g) Disciplinary

The Registrar's disciplinary function as Chairman of the Junior Staff Appointments, Promotions and Disciplinary Committee is derived from the authority of Council.

h) Ceremonial

The Registrar is the statutory Master of Ceremony at all university functions like convocation.

Awosisi (2020), further adds as follows:

- i) The Registrar represents and stands on behalf of the University in Law Courts or Tribunals when there is litigation.
- j) The Registrar is the Official Letter writer and Spokesman of the University
- k) The Registrar is the Official Curator and Keeper-in Chief of ALL Records, especially sensitive ones such as Statutes, Title Deeds, MoUs Agreements, Panel reports, Certificates, etc.

The main goal of the Registrar's Department is to render effective and efficient service. By virtue of its role as a service centre, every staff in the Department should strive to be better than the best in the input-output process. The tempo of work in the University, generally, and the Registry in Particular, is such that staff are always under pressure, pressure to get matters ready for implementation, pressure to process examination results, pressure to take administrative decisions on various issues, etc. Services in the Registry must therefore be quick and carried out with utmost dispatch at all times.

The University Community is a highly critical and meticulous community. The staff of the Registrar's Department must therefore leave no one in doubt as to the reliability of the decisions they present, the information they give, and the results they produce.

It is little wonder then that, despite the integral role and functions of the professional administrators, there has been a lot of outcry in the university system about the jobs being gradually taken over by the academics, thereby threatening their continued existence in the university system in the long run.

The succeeding paragraphs would attempt to provide the factors that are responsible for this trend. This is as many administrators have lamented at the slightest opportunity that their schedules are being taken over. This is why it has become one of the most discussed issues at most professional conferences and workshops recently, and there are indications that the problems cut across all universities.

Erosion of Statutory Functions of Professional Administrators in Nigerian University System: Factors Responsible and its Effect in the Nigerian University System.

According to Akanji (2000), there was time in the history of Universities in Nigeria which was described as the golden age of Registrars in Nigerian universities which spanned between 1948 to the early 1980s. By then, virtually all matters of staff were handled by the Registrar as Registrars were the faces of universities in almost all matters (Akanji, 2000).

That, this is no longer the case, as the erosion of the functions (power) of Registrars started subtly by the mid-1980s after the unrest at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

That the Abisoye Committee was expected to look at the problem recommended among other things, recommended that a Student Affairs Deanery be created in the Office of the Vice-Chancellor with a Dean to be appointed to head such Division and report directly to the Vice-Chancellor. With the acceptance of the Abisoye recommendation, that very important Unit of the registry was removed from the control of the Registrar.

According to Akanji (2000), as if that was not enough, universities, one after the other, started transferring units like the Legal Unit, the Information and Protocol Unit, the Health services Unit, and the Works and Maintenance Unit from the Office of the Registrar to that of the Vice Chancellor. Later, the Academic Planning Unit was transferred from the Registry to the Vice Chancellor's Office.

Babalola (2017), stated that if the academics do not access sound, qualitative and well responsive administrators, it used to lead many of them into combining academics with administration, thereby reducing or compromising their potentials and capacities to produce the appropriate results. As long as the academics will need professionals to document their decisions, carry out the implementation of specific regulations, guide and take study of specific institutional issues and responsibilities, implement policies and programmes, serving meetings and represent the university in activities of less academic nature, then, the job of administrators and other support staff cannot be set aside or totally eliminated.

Furthermore, Adegbite (2007), stated that if the university community is made up of only the academic staff, who are the teachers and researchers, then the working of the system will not be complete because the administrators and bureaucrats also have a stake in the system.

According to Bakare (2019), positions like those of the Dean, Student Affairs Division, and Director, Academic Planning were once manned by administrators as Directors. Today, in some universities.

So what factors could be responsible for this trend? Akanji (2000), identified some of the factors responsible for the erosion of the Registrars functions as follows:

- 1 Government (Proprietors)
- 2 The introduction of the tenure system to the position of the Registrar. In the past, Registrar's hold office till retirement. This enabled a lot of stability and the concept of institutional memory is easily achieved.
- 3 The government succumbed to the pressure of the staff unions (who are mainly Registry staff) and first reduced the tenure to a maximum of ten years (5 x 2) in 1993 and then to five years with an "uninsured" possibility of an additional one year in 2012.

In addition to the above, there is the possibility of the Registrars and other administrators being overwhelmed by their schedules and failing in their duties due to not upholding the following attributes when carrying out their schedules:

1. The level of Education of Administrators (Credentials and Expertise) Professional Administrators are expected to be knowledgeable of rules, regulations, culture, and tradition for the smooth functioning of the university.
2. Skills Acquisition and Training (Training and Self Development). It is expected that Professional Administrators possess very critical skills like communication skills (oral and written), organizational skills, time management skills, demonstrate strong interpersonal skills, and provide broader skills beyond the traditional scope.
3. Work Input and Performance Output (Quality of Work and Exposure)
4. Work Specialization (Professionalism)
5. Work Standards (Quality Assurance and Competence)
6. Personal Conduct (Integrity)
7. Social Obligations (Commitment and Partnership)

The immediate implication of this, as stated by Akanji (2000), is the availability of a vast pool of knowledgeable personnel that are wasting away. The system is suffering for it. Furthermore, Akanji (2000), went on to say that the transfer of the Student Affairs Division from the Registry to the Vice-Chancellor's Office had not reduced the spate of violent demonstrations by university students. If anything, it has removed the benefit of advice that could come if it passes through the Registrar. It could be argued that there is still a representative of the Registrar, who serves as Student Affairs Officer in the Unit, but the ultimate authority still resides with the Dean, who reports directly to the Vice-Chancellor.

Some Vice-Chancellors when they have disagreements with their Registrars tend to sabotage such Registrars in the performance of the latter's duties. For example, they go around the Registrars to get things done by patronizing the Registrar's subordinates. We have seen instances where Deputy Registrars or even lower cadre officers are used to undermine Registrars. In many universities, as we have noted above, the Legal Unit is in the Vice-Chancellor's office, yet Registrars are expected to represent the university in court. The Information Unit is in Vice-Chancellor's office, and the Registrar is the spokesperson of the University. Some of our Registrars have a poor understanding of where their allegiance should be. Some Registrars play staff against each other and discriminate in the dispensation of favours among their staff.

Conclusion

Based on the above review, it can be said that there has been gradual erosion and usurpation of the roles and functions of the registrar and professional administrators in the Nigerian universities. This has contributed to the transfers of some units to the office of the Vice Chancellor like Students Affairs, Academic Planning, Information and Protocol, Legal, Security, etc.

Recommendations

Awosisi (2020), recommended as follows which is in line with this review:

1. Be a problem solver

A professional university administrator should develop problem-solving skills and employ methods by creating values that contribute to overall effectiveness and exerting control over the work environment.

A problem solver would diagnose the current state of the workplace environment, as he/she may not be comfortable with the status quo. The administrator identifies factors and forces influencing it, develop and implement approaches and alternatives to bring about the needed change for achieving stated objectives.

The university environment is changing rapidly due to internal and external demands; therefore, a professional university administrator should change with time. The serious issue of paucity of funds should act as a wakeup call for the administrator to think of other means of improving performances at no extra cost to the university.

2. Improve Efficiency

The university's professional administrator should be vastly knowledgeable in new technology and work towards improving technology efficiency and quality service delivery to all stakeholders.

3. Show Initiative

According to Mary Kay Ash, American business woman, (Art Quotes blog) “there are three types of people in this world: those who make things happen, those who watch things happen and those who wonder what happened”, the professional university administrator most likely belongs to the first group of people. Initiative correlates strongly with personal achievement and professional development.

A professional university administrator must therefore develop ideas to simplify processes, proactively suggest improvements and take decisive action.

4. Engaging technology and life-long learning

Professional administrators should continue to upgrade their skills to fill the gap between today, tomorrow, and the future. Therefore, lifelong learning is key to remaining relevant in the 21st century.

It's a common saying that, "You cannot give what you do not have ".

5. Improve Quality of service

Modern technology has ensured the availability of many tool effective applications that enhance performance. Optimisation of processes translates to a quicker pace for getting things done. However, increasing speed volume is no longer enough but rather taking the right decisions, making good connections, risk taking and insight all contribute to creating value, making an impact and providing quality service.

6. In-depth knowledge of the university

The professional university administrator, as a repository of knowledge, must have in-depth knowledge of the history, processes, insights, practices, values, traditions, rules, and regulations (both written and unwritten) of the university system. Values could be created by leveraging knowledge about the on-going process, learning from past challenges and successes in strategic decision-making, and sharing experiences with stakeholders. In developing solutions and making the best decisions, values added to the university which improves service delivery.

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